

**Researching and Modelling Anticommons and its
Potential Relevance to Bankruptcy: A Game-Theoretic
Analysis.**

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Abstract

The tragedy of the anticommons occurs when multiple parties hold exclusion rights over a shared resource, leading to underuse. This paper explores whether anticommons is useful in explaining growing inefficiencies in modern bankruptcy, where creditor interests have increasingly become less aligned. Despite its relevance, only Baird and Rasmussen (2010) have suggested anticommons as a lens for bankruptcy - literature and analysis on the topic is light. This paper addresses this gap by assessing existing literature and adapting game-theoretic models to bankruptcy: Baird and Rasmussen's model, Buchanan and Yoon's (2000) anticommons model, and Yoon and Shughart's (2013) Stackelberg anticommons model. These adaptations reveal that the current fragmented environment in bankruptcy paired with excludability rights (often found in bankruptcy) can destroy company value. This is more pronounced with the Stackelberg anticommons model. This paper brings legal and economic theories together to advance theoretical understanding and quantify inefficiencies in the bankruptcy application.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	5
2. Literature Review.....	9
2.1 Anticommons.....	9
2.1.1 Introduction:.....	9
2.1.3 Experiments and Models:	13
2.1.4 The Possibility of Overuse:.....	14
2.1.5 The Applicability of Anticommons to Bankruptcy:	15
2.2 Distressed Debt	17
2.2.1 Introduction:.....	17
2.2.2 The Changing Landscape:.....	17
2.2.3 Bargaining and Bankruptcy:.....	18
2.2.4 The US Bankruptcy Code:.....	19
3. A Game-Theoretic Analysis of the Baird-Rasmussen Model.....	21
4. Game-Theoretic Anticommons Models.....	25
4.1 Simple (Bertrand) Anticommons Game	25
4.2 Stackelberg Anticommons Game	27
4.3 The Optimal Result	29
4.4 Social Welfare	31
4.5 Comparison of the Results	31
5. Simple and Stackelberg Anticommons Games in Bankruptcy.....	35
6. Conclusion	41
7. Bibliography	44

1. Introduction

Anticommons is defined as a property regime where there are multiple owners, and more than one owner is able to exclude others from a scarce resource. This is problematic because it regularly results in underuse – a phenomenon known as the *tragedy of the anticommons* – where scarce resources are underused because too many owners have excludability rights (Heller, 1998).

To illustrate anticommons, and tragedy of the anticommons, Fennell's (2004) garden and lock example can be used. Imagine a private garden in London. The garden is jointly owned by ten people, and to use the garden one must ask all ten people for permission. To enforce this, the garden has a gate which is locked by 10 different padlocks. To enter the garden, you need all ten keys. This represents an anticommons. Imagine someone wishes to use this garden. To do so, they must obtain the agreement from all owners – some of whom may wish to charge for the privilege. Any one owner may set an unreasonably high price, or may say no. Even without this there is significant cost involved with contacting and negotiating with ten different owners. This excludability feature demonstrated is highly likely to lead to underuse of the garden. This is tragedy of the anticommons.

Following Heller's 1998 paper, Anticommons became a widely researched topic amongst academics from the subjects of Law, Economics, Politics and Psychology. Its applications have spanned many fields such as patenting, technology, healthcare, property, and bankruptcy. While much of the research remains theoretical, some models have been applied and several experimental research projects undertaken.

Despite the wide research on anticommons, the output is overshadowed by the opposite regime, *commons*, and the associated *tragedy of the commons*. This is proven by a simple google search. Searching 'Tragedy of the Commons' yields approximately 189,000,000 results. Searching 'Tragedy of the Anticommons' returns only 31,700. This discrepancy would not matter if the tragedy of the anticommons was significantly rarer than tragedy of the commons or resulted in less severe outcomes.

This is simply not the case. Experimental research indicates that the outcome from anticommons is at least as severe as that of the commons and that, even with prior education, underuse in anticommons is more likely than overuse in commons (when both are possible; Vanneste et Al., 2006; Dhont et Al., 2012).

Anticommons has been suggested by Baird and Rasmussen (2010) as a lens to understand inefficiencies in bankruptcy. Despite the suggestion, this application has received no other analysis. Therefore, this paper aims to investigate whether models for anticommons are able and are useful in analysing inefficiencies in distressed debt¹ and bankruptcy. Specifically, it examines how fragmented creditor interests and excludability effect theoretical outcomes. These excludability rights are common due to the US bankruptcy code. The code requires certain majorities in both number of creditors and value of debt agreeing to a reorganisation for it to pass. Game-theoretic models are used to analyse how different scenarios influence bankruptcy and reorganisation. In doing so, this paper aims to bridge the gap between existing legal and economic literature on anticommons, and existing literature on fragmented creditor interests.

Bankruptcy plays an important role in financial markets by ensuring firms that are failing to meet their obligations are disbanded or reorganised in the most efficient way. This maximises profit for debt holders and destroys the least value in the reorganised or liquidated company. This paper will focus on reorganisation rather than liquidation. This is because reorganisation is almost twice as prevalent as liquidation (Khan and Longoria, 2025). That said, the analysis is very similar for both because the same fragmented interests and excludability rights impact the liquidation of the company too.

Historically, the interests of the holders of debt in distressed and bankrupt companies have been assumed to have aligned interests. This assumption is key to the way the bankruptcy process has been designed and until recently, has been an accurate

¹ Throughout this paper, distressed debt refers to debt either held in a bankrupt company or in a company near bankruptcy. For a discussion on definitions of distressed debt see Altman and Behenni (2019).

assumption. Lately, however, distressed credit markets have become fragmented. Incentives and interests now have the potential to be thoroughly opposing (Adler et Al., 2018). This has stemmed from a more complex financial world with complex financial instruments, equally complex financial strategies, and contract textualism² (Baird and Rasmussen, 2010). The impact of the fragmentation is creditors fighting each other for larger slices of a pie rather than working together to make the pie bigger (Talley and Pandya, 2023).

To summarise, the key contribution of this paper is the integration of economic and legal academic research and using this to adapt an anticommons model to bankruptcy. This will be achieved by accomplishing the following aims:

1. Defining the anticommons problem and outlining its theoretical foundation.
2. Explaining what bankruptcy is, highlighting its main features, and describing the recent changes affecting it.
3. Showing that anticommons can be used to suggest inefficiencies in bankruptcy.
4. Evaluating the applicability and usefulness of existing anticommons models in explaining inefficiencies in bankruptcy.

Specifically, three game-theoretic models will be investigated – Baird and Rasmussen’s (2010) model; Buchanan and Yoon’s (2000) Bertrand Anticommons model; and Yoon and Shughart’s (2013) Stackelberg Anticommons model. The latter two models will be adapted for use in bankruptcy. From these, the paper will quantify underuse and compare it to a profit optimal result. This will show that anticommons destroys value for reorganised companies, and that a Stackelberg anticommons destroys more value than that of a simple anticommons. This result allows for the conclusion that bankruptcy can present a tragedy of the anticommons.

² Contract textualism is where words are taken for their exact meaning - as written. This can lead to sentences or words being taken too literally and consequently legal debate over the wording of contracts.

Since this work is expanding the applications of anticommons, this paper may contribute to economic and financial law research. These insights can be used to guide future research on the legal, financial, and regulatory implications. Further work may encourage revisions to the US bankruptcy code and therefore help to stem the loss of value coming from disjointed reorganisations.

2. Literature Review

This section will provide an overview of anticommons, including its history, applications, models, and criticisms. This background is helpful in understanding how anticommons relates to underuse through models, experiments, and applications. In turn, this helps inform its relevancy to bankruptcy. By addressing the strengths and critiques of anticommons in different applications, the groundwork is laid for the newer application of bankruptcy. It can then be shown that the ingredients for anticommons are present in bankruptcy – with the likely result being underuse.

2.1 Anticommons

2.1.1 Introduction:

Anticommons was first introduced by Michael Heller in the context of property rights (in his 1998 article "The Tragedy of the Anticommons: Property in the Transition from Marx to Markets" - Heller, 1998). The concept has been expanded to cover a wide range of topics including biosciences, technology, property, and theoretical experiments. The concept is still an active source of literature today.

To describe the foundation of anticommons, it makes sense to first look at its foundational concepts. The first foundational concept was the well-known Tragedy of the Commons introduced by Hardin (1968). The paper was the first to describe how individual maximisation of utility could have dire consequences for resource-sharing groups - overutilisation. This came from everyone having the right to use and no one having the right to exclude. The main examples given include cows grazing in fields, pollution of waters and atmospheres and overfishing. The significance of this comes from the fact that everyone is in resource-sharing groups to an extent – everyone shares water and the atmosphere for example. The cost of overpollution is small to individuals or companies but great to society as a whole.

The second important concept came from Michelman's (1982) paper investigating ethics and economics in property rights. He described a 'regulatory regime', where everyone has rights relating to the object in the regime – the exact opposite of the definition of commons given above – hence the title 'anticommons'. It is believed that this theory was not pursued further in 1982 because the definition was too literal – and exact examples of a situation fitting to this definition do not exist (Heller, 1998). Arguably, the paper falls short because Michelman (and other property theorists) did not recognise the potential their work had. Sixteen years thereafter, and with only minor adjustments, their work became the sprawling anticommons debate.

In 1998, Heller went on to release his first paper on the subject of anticommons. This paper suggested a more useful definition for anticommons:

"A property regime in which multiple owners hold effective rights of exclusion in a scarce resource." (Heller, 1998, p.668).

It also provided a definition for tragedy of the anticommons:

"When there are too many owners holding rights of exclusion, the resource is prone to underuse." (Heller, 1998, p.624).

This definition is more applicable because it takes away the suggestion that anticommons (and underuse) is an optimal result and the suggestion that everyone must have equal excludability rights. These two suggestions allow the new definition to be applicable to bankruptcy – this will be seen later in an applied example. In reality, there is no need for all owners to have excludability rights for underuse of a scarce resource to be the result. A final advancement of this paper was the move away from formal legal rights into a more informal framework.

2.1.2 Applications:

Heller's first anticommons paper described shop stalls lining the streets of Moscow whilst shopfronts behind the stalls lay empty. Amid increasing privatisation, various rights and permits for each shop were divided and distributed to multiple stakeholders. These included the right to sell, the right to occupy and the right to sales revenue and many others – even informal excludability rights in the form of 'protection' offered by the mafia. Setting up stalls in front of these shops avoided this problem. The tragedy of the anticommons was extremely easy to see in this argument where multiple stakeholders had excludability rights to each individual shop. This was aggravated by excludability rights not being easily transferable due to a corrupt and complex government (Heller, 1998). This meant shop owners could not simply buy all the permits they needed to run a shop.

Whilst the underuse in the streets of Moscow is clearly harmful, there is a counter to Heller's implication that underuse is always harmful. Bell and Parchomovsky (2003) are the first authors to suggest that the results of anticommons can be good. They make the argument that split excludability rights can serve the public. Underuse of green land in cities may be viewed as unfortunate to developers but to the public provides much needed space for recreation. The paper points to the fact that anticommons in property is not always a tragedy – using the example of central park in New York where nearby landowners and the public would thwart any attempt to develop the land. This argument is applicable to any area where overdevelopment is a concern.

The most investigated application for anticommons is in patents – more specifically patents in biomedical research (Heller, 2013). This was first explored by Heller and Eisenberg (1998). The paper was based around a potential Alzheimer's cure that had to be shelved due to requiring a list of patents to make it. Each patent-holder had an excludability right in the drug – without any one patent, the drug could not be produced. Each patent holder could extort as much value as possible from the drug

producer. It is easy to see the underuse in this example, and the loss to society. It is almost impossible to argue that this underuse is positive to society, but the extent to which this is a problem in drug discovery has been debated.

Many other authors have made similar arguments in the field of biomedical innovation and have reached similar conclusions. For example, Burk and Lemley (2009) concluded that the biomedical patent area is at high risk of anticommons. They argued that this has come from the lack of industry specific patents - patents designed for use in information technologies are being applied to biomedical research. The author's argument is closely related to the argument this paper makes with bankruptcy – the bankruptcy code has been designed with a set of assumptions in mind that may no longer be applicable.

However, Walsh et Al. (2005) found that drug discovery had not been substantially impeded by the increasing number of patents. Patent pools, government, philanthropic and charitable funding for biomedical research has often provided sufficient money for purchasing patents and patent groups. This implies that as soon as the potential impact of anticommons in medical research was seen, a number of funders sought to alleviate the problem. That said, relying on charitable and government funding to alleviate anticommons cannot be classed as a long-term and reliable solution. Burk and Lemley's suggestion of industry specific patenting laws appears to be the better long-term solution.

Another patent anticommons application is in the technology industry. Ziedonis (2003) investigates the use of patents in the technology industry and concludes that anticommons applies here too. The main advance in this paper is to suggest that the threat of overlapping patents to technology companies makes them more likely to aggressively patent around innovations. This allows them more space for their own future innovation but exacerbates anticommons by restricting the ability of other companies to innovate easily and affordably.

Strong evaluation to this sprawl of patenting is given by Lemley and Shapiro (2005). They make the argument that any aggressive over patenting has a simple solution – legal action. Any unjustifiable patent is declared a weak patent and should not be difficult to contest in court. This creates a legal cost to the aggressively patenting company and should ensure that companies only patent what they truly deserve and can defend – limiting anticommons in the process.

2.1.3 Experiments and Models:

Modelling of anticommons has been around for almost as long as anticommons itself. The first paper published on this was Buchanan and Yoon's (2000) application of a Bertrand model to anticommons. The authors prove that profit, usage, and price charged all tend to zero as the number of possible excluders increases. The paper suggests that the tragedy of the anticommons can be measured by unrealised economic value and that this is symmetric to the unrealised economic value that comes from multiple access rights in the tragedy of the commons. This paper falters by failing to algebraically calculate this unrealised economic value. This paper will further study Buchanan and Yoon's model to quantify the loss to society and adapt the model for bankruptcy.

This symmetry is refuted by Vanneste et Al. (2006), who suggest that the outcome under anticommons is far more severe than that in the tragedy of the commons. This is backed up by two experimental studies. The first study was set up as a board game where players had an endowment of cash and property. Some of the property was subject to a commons problem and some to an anticommons problem. This tested and compared the amount of money required to solve both issues - that were otherwise identical. The study showed that participants demanded a greater amount of money in an anticommons property regime than in a common's regime. Study two investigated whether study one's results had anything to do with lack of knowledge on the dangers of underuse. It used a passage and questionnaire where the passage described both the dangers of underuse and overuse and then presented participants

with an endowment to take resources out of a commons and give-up/ buy excludability rights. The study confirmed that the amount requested in anticommons is higher than the equivalent in commons; and suggests that the result is not because of a lack of understanding of anticommons. This conclusion makes the comparative lack of research into anticommons all the more confusing.

That said, Dhont et Al. (2012) had substantially different findings. Using two different methodologies (one/two shot games), they hypothesised and proved that by highlighting externalities and the benefits of cooperation, more cooperative solutions were reached in an anticommons dilemma. This means there is some academic debate over whether highlighting the dangers of underuse improves cooperation.

Finally, Yoon and Shughart (2013) followed up on Buchanan and Yoon's (2000) initial paper. They suggested that a Stackelberg model may be a more applicable model for anticommons in some situations. Their argument uses the example of river tolls that covered much of the river Danube centuries ago. Each toll had the incentive to charge as much as possible because no boat could pass without paying their toll (excludability). The result was a series of tolls so expensive that shipping down the river halted. The authors show that a Stackelberg anticommons is much more severe – as the number of excluders increase, profit and usage tend to zero faster than in a simple anticommons. This model will also be advanced by this paper.

2.1.4 The Possibility of Overuse:

So far, only application specific evaluation has been given. One key argument in anticommons literature is that anticommons can lead to overuse as well as underuse. This argument is similar to Lemley and Shapiro's (2005) point mentioned under patents; and was first developed by Fennell (2004). The author states that there is a significant free rider problem in the enforcement of excludability. If excludability rights are fragmented, each person may sit back and not wish to be involved in legal or other proceedings to stop improper use of a resource. Imagine a shared tennis

court that requires five keys to enter (one from each owner). A person may unlawfully use the court by jumping a fence. To stop this, money (for CCTV/ better fences or locks) and legal enforcement is required. The lack of enforcement due to the free rider problem implies little to no punishment for improper usage. This implies the potential for overuse, not underuse.

This argument applies well in personal situations – property for example. However, it is hard to imagine that in business situations the same would be true. If a patent is being infringed and this is costing a company, then it would be rare for the company to sit back and ignore it due to idleness.

A year later, Buzbee (2005) developed Fennell's argument. The author added that any complex regulatory framework for a resource has high potential for overlapping regulatory agencies in both vertical and horizontal senses. For example, you may have local council and national council both policing an issue (vertical) as well as two different local councils having overlap in policing (horizontal). This can lead to improper handling of excludability rights. If this is the case, then overuse could potentially continue regardless of the anticommons problem.

Fennell's (2004) and Buzbee's (2005) papers suggest that restrictions must be enforced properly for underuse to be the result of anticommons. In bankruptcy, it is expected that restrictions are enforced due to the possible monetary loss from not enforcing.

2.1.5 The Applicability of Anticommons to Bankruptcy:

The final application is imperative to this paper. This is the only application of anticommons to bankruptcy, described by Baird and Rasmussen (2010). This application is just as far reaching as the heavier researched areas. Like other forms of anticommons, the authors do not make the argument that all bankruptcy's involve

anticommons and underuse. The argument is that the area, bankruptcy, is susceptible to anticommons and that the result of this can be harmful to society.

Baird and Rasmussen reach the conclusion of anticommons in the following way. They lay out a complex new environment where debt holder's interests are fragmented. They make the argument that this is because of complex financial derivatives and strategies. They also make the argument that coalition formation is harder because of such differing strategies – if incentives are not perfectly aligned then a coalition with other debt holders does not make sense.

The paper makes the argument that bankruptcy law was and has never been well equipped to deal with these changes to credit and claims³. In bankruptcy, there is often an intuitive assumption that an investor with some form of control in a company acts to maximise the value of the company. The paper rejects this notion, using the case of Credit Default Swaps⁴ (CDS). The buyer of the CDS now holds the credit risk but not the control usually associated with this. In fact, one does not need to hold the underlying bond to create a CDS – it is common for more CDSs to exist than underlying bonds (Baird and Rasmussen, 2010). There may be a stakeholder, invested in a company, who is set to benefit from the default of that company. This party has no interest in maximising the value of the company.

Finally, the paper discusses cooperation of party's involved in a bankruptcy under the assumption that the bankrupt company has managed to identify the party's involved and their economic interests. It makes the point that finding an acceptable solution should now be easy – but rarely is. To show this, a written model using the concepts of bargaining theory and the problem of the empty core is utilised. The following section will address this model.

³In fact, the bankruptcy code only specifically mentions secured claims, unsecured claims, and interests.

⁴ This derivative allows the credit risk in a company to be traded separately to the underlying loan but the rights to the company (voting for example) remain with the bond holder.

This paper's conclusions on misaligned incentives of creditors give the first piece of the building block to the tragedy of the anticommons. Creditors have no interest to work together and if excludability rights did exist, they would have an incentive to use these to achieve their own goals for the company. However, the authors spend too little time explaining where the excludability rights come from. This paper will make the argument that they are baked into the US bankruptcy code. This comes from the code's requirement for certain majorities for any reorganisation to be ratified. Any creditor that can stop the required majority has excludability rights.

2.2 Distressed Debt

2.2.1 Introduction:

Altman is a key author in the distressed debt and loan market, having made significant contributions to this field for over 35 years. He was the first author to publish a complete guide to distressed debt investing (Altman, 1991); acknowledging early on the potential for outsized returns in this asset class. This perspective was supported by earlier work from Ramaswami and Moeller (1990) who identified a link between good investment decisions and higher investment returns. This implication is important because it explains how and why specialist distressed debt (and bankruptcy) investors came about. Good investment decisions imply higher investment returns, and specialisation could mean better decisions and outsized returns.

2.2.2 The Changing Landscape:

Distressed debt markets have changed significantly in the past thirty years. This has been acknowledged by both Baird and Rasmussen (2010) and Altman and Benhenni (2019). Baird and Rasmussen outlined how the likely holders of secured debt have shifted from a single bank to a multitude of banks and specialist debt investors. They

also outlined significant changes in the strategies and incentives of these investors, from pure bankruptcy to the use of complex hedging and betting derivatives. Altman and Benhenni's contribution focuses on showing how drastically the amount of distressed debt has increased in the last 30 years. This has in turn increased the importance of successful restructuring. These papers begin to paint the picture of the changing distressed debt market.

The type of investor that holds distressed debt can have a big impact on performance. This was first investigated by Hotchkiss and Mooradian (1997). The authors looked at 288 companies post-restructuring and studied the impact of an activist distressed debt specialist on performance. They found that the presence of an activist significantly improved performance. This study has been reaffirmed more recently by Jiang et Al (2012), who conducted a similar study. The authors found a comparable increase in performance with the involvement of an active Hedge Fund. They also found that under these conditions, companies were more likely to lose their exclusive restructuring rights, lose their CEO's, and successfully emerge from bankruptcy. This implies that activist investors are more aggressive in their strategies. Whitman and Diz (2009) previously discovered the benefit for debt holders to controlling a bankrupt company. Consequently, incentive misalignment with other less aggressive distressed debt investors is likely.

2.2.3 Bargaining and Bankruptcy:

A key theme in this paper is the change to creditor incentives and alignment in recent years. Baird and Rasmussen (2010) talked much about the evolution of distressed debt markets, and the implications this had for bargaining theory (and the possibility for an empty core). They did not know how much more relevant this would become in light of a very recent phenomenon within distressed debt markets and bargaining – creditor-on-creditor violence and debt textualism. This is outlined by Franklin Templeton (2024) who suggest that the US is much more susceptible to misalignment of creditor interests and subsequent legal battles due to their bankruptcy laws. This

explains why the US is the best and most important place to study anticommons and its application to bankruptcy.

This analysis suggests that the relevance of this paper in other developed areas of the world may be limited. Much of the research into bankruptcy and inefficiencies has been based on the US. This means that it is more difficult to produce an analysis that applies to other areas of the world. The lack of research may indicate a lack of inefficiencies to investigate. Either way, the topic of inefficiencies in bankruptcy across developed nations could certainly benefit from future academic research.

Talley and Pandya (2023) have made a vital contribution to the creditor misalignment area. They argue that one factor in this is the result of judges taking the exact words of the contract – textualism. This, combined with an extensive period of cheap funding and loosely worded credit documents has led to an explosion of legal bargaining and debate over credit agreements. This provides the first ingredient needed for anticommons to appear in the bankruptcy setting – disagreement amongst creditors.

2.2.4 The US Bankruptcy Code:

To see where excludability rights may come from, it is first useful to understand bankruptcy. The following is based on Chapter 11 of United States Bankruptcy Code.

When a company declares bankruptcy, liabilities due are frozen and stakeholders negotiate whether to liquidate the company or workout a viable way for the business to continue in the long term. Pay-outs from bankruptcy are paid in order of seniority of the capital structure. Secured credit is repaid first, then bankruptcy costs/fees, then junior credit and finally equity. Each section may have multiple classes to be paid and more complex capital structures may have more instruments than those listed.

In all bankruptcies there exists at least one fulcrum debt class. Below this class, debtors will receive nothing and above this class, debtors will be fully repaid. In the fulcrum class(es), debt will be repaid with remaining funds after all classes above have

been paid (it will be repaid at 1-99% of face value). A debtor projected to be at least somewhat repaid has a say in the terms of the reorganisation/ liquidation of the bankrupt business. In any deal, the following applies to fulcrum debt holders:

- Holders with 75% of the debt or more must vote in favour of the agreement.
- Half or more of the absolute number of creditors must vote in favour of the agreement.
- Creditors in classes of debt that are identical or near identical must be treated equally to each other.

If these conditions are met, a judge can approve the bankruptcy agreement - even if some creditors are against it. This is called a cramdown. This implies that any debt holder (or group of debt holders) with 25% of the debt can stop any reorganisation from happening. The same is true of any group of debt holders that make up more than half of the number of debt holders. In all three situations the (groups of) debt holders have excludability rights. These rights, combined with misaligned incentives, are the second and final ingredient needed to suggest anticommons to analyse bankruptcy.

3. A Game-Theoretic Analysis of the Baird-Rasmussen Model

The following model shows how creditor misalignment may lead to loss of value for a reorganising company. It is based on Baird and Rasmussen's 2010 paper, where a verbal description of a model is given, framed in cooperative game theory. The model is as follows:

There is one bankrupt company, and three stakeholders invested in that company – a Hedge Fund, a Supplier, and a Manager. All three stakeholders are able to add value to the company. The company owes the Supplier and the Hedge Fund \$10 each - with the Supplier holding unsecured debt and the Hedge Fund holding secured debt. If the company was liquidated, \$15 would be recovered. From this, the Manager would earn \$2 for overseeing, the Hedge Fund would earn \$10 because its debt is secured, and the Supplier would receive the remaining \$3 - it is last in line. These amounts are central to the verbal model as they represent the minimum amount any stakeholder must receive in an alternative situation. If an alternative is worse, they will not cooperate because they receive more under liquidation. Stakeholders must decide whether to cooperate or not – at least two must cooperate to add value. Full cooperation yields a total company value of \$24 whilst cooperation between two stakeholders yields values between \$20 and \$23. All stakeholders know these payoffs.

The importance of this model is due to the lack of 'a core'. In every situation, there is an incentive for a stakeholder to approach another stakeholder and form a separate partnership, sharing the excess payoff from leaving out the final stakeholder. This leaves an empty core (Coase, 1960; Tesler, 1994) – which this paper will show diagrammatically.

Key: Hedge fund (HF), Supplier (S), Manager (M)

Figure 1 - Diagrammatic Explanation of Core Theory

In these circumstances, and with the assumption that negotiations and coalition forming are cost free, no agreement will be reached. This shows the complexities in forming partnerships in bankruptcy.

However, this model has significant limitations. Firstly, the model does not account for excludability rights which are central to the anticommons and tragedy of the anticommons argument. An excluded stakeholder cannot stop a reorganisation going through without them – they can only try to incentivise a different organisation including them. Secondly, the model is framed with cooperative game theory. This is despite the fact that the whole paper is making the argument that due to the changing credit environment, incentives amongst creditors are no longer aligned and creditors are regularly unwilling to cooperate in standard creditor partnerships and agreements (Baird and Rasmussen, 2010; Adler et Al., 2018).

In an attempt to solve the issue of cooperation, this paper suggests a one-shot game adapted from the Baird and Rasmussen verbal model. This will allow the model to be analysed in a non-cooperative game which may be more accurate.

		Player 1 - Hedge Fund											
		Y			N								
Y/N Denotes Partnership		Player 3 - Manager											
Payoffs in order: 1, 2, 3		Y			N								
Player 2 - Supplier	Y	13	6	5	14	7	2	10	6	4	10	3	2
	N	16	3	3	10	3	2	10	3	2	10	3	2

Figure 2 - Payoff Table

From this, it can be shown that there are two Nash Equilibriums (NE)– all players entering the partnership and all players rejecting the partnership (in bold). Two-person partnerships are no longer a feasible outcome under normal game theory assumptions. In this game any one player can threaten to reject the deal in an attempt to extract value. If the other players believe that a player will select ‘no’ then their best response is to select no – it is the dominant strategy to this belief. This may suggest that the game will lead to liquidation and loss of value from not reorganising the company.

Upon reflection of the game proposed, it quickly became clear that it possessed several flaws:

Firstly, the game assumes that each player benefits from the company succeeding. This assumption is limiting – as discussed previously, financial strategies are increasingly complex, and payoffs have the potential to increase with a company’s failure. The assumptions in the building of this game narrow the applications of this model. That said, if payoffs are measurable then it would be possible to alter the assumptions and payoffs. The framework used is still meaningful.

Secondly, by limiting this to a one-shot game much of the strategic interaction between players is lost. Both Adler et Al. (2018) and Talley and Pandya (2023) mention that contractual ambiguity and legal debate can lead to multiple rounds of renegotiation. This dynamic is much more difficult to model using this framework – even a multiple round game would require payoffs to be allocated each round which would not fit with such a situation with constant renegotiation. Whilst this model may not be able to take dynamic renegotiating into account, it could be argued that the single shot game represents each stakeholder negotiating all possible options open to them and then deciding based on their beliefs. This may still be sufficient in simpler bankruptcy scenarios.

Finally, and most importantly, the game in this format lacks excludability rights – without this, anticommons cannot be properly analysed. Whilst this model represents the inefficiency from misalignment of creditor incentives, a more complex model that is better able to model excludability is needed. This leads onto the next section of this paper where two models will be introduced. The cost of anticommons is measurable in these models.

4. Game-Theoretic Anticommons Models

The following section will investigate two game-theoretic models that have been applied to the anticommons subject. The terms inside these models (and some basic rules) will then be changed to make them applicable to bankruptcy. By only changing the terms and adding rules, the results found without the bankruptcy adaptation will still apply after the adaptation. This will help the paper to deduce underuse and tragedy of the anticommons as a potential result of bankruptcy.

Both the Bertrand Anticommons model (referred to as the simple model throughout this paper), and the Stackelberg Model, use the story of a car park to explain the harm of anticommons. In the simple model, both owners have equal rights over ownership, excludability, and pricing. This model can be used to explain bankruptcy situations where owners have equal ownership, rights, and demands over reorganisation or liquidation. In the Stackelberg model, each successive owner only has excludability rights over owners below them in a priority ordering (like a toll on the river Danube). This means earlier owners have more pricing power and excludability rights, and therefore more of a right to ownership. This model can be used for more complex bankruptcy scenarios. An example of this may be where successive debt holders own less and less debt and therefore have less say in proceedings.

4.1 Simple (Bertrand) Anticommons Game

Firstly, this paper considers the simple anticommons model first introduced by Buchanan and Yoon (2000). The following equations and analysis are based on their paper – no adaptations have been made at this stage.

The model considers a large empty space in a town that can be used for parking. The value a potential customer gets from parking in this car park decreases as the number of cars already parked there increases. That is: $P_T = a - bQ$ where P_T is the total

price a potential customer is willing to pay and Q is the number of users of the car park at any one time. a & b are constants.

Imagine that two people own the car park and that an alternative exists with free parking a mile away from the town. Both owners have the right to exclude any or all car park users – to do so they set an unreasonably high price. Users of the car park require parking tickets from both owners.

This makes: $P_T = P_1 + P_2 = a - bQ$

Assume that players act rationally; and that costs are zero so revenue is equal to profit. Profit and revenue will be used interchangeably from here. To determine the optimal price charged, profit (P_1Q) for player 1 will be maximised with respect to player 2's choice of price. This is assuming revenue maximising behaviour for both players.

This results in: $P_1Q = \frac{P_1(a-P_1-P_2)}{b}$

Taking first order conditions with respect to P_1 yields: $\frac{(a-P_1-P_2)-P_1}{b} = 0$

Rearranging for P_1 : $P_1 = \frac{a-P_2}{2}$

This solution is symmetric for P_1 and P_2 so: $P_2 = \frac{a-P_1}{2}$

The solution for P_1 can be substituted into P_2 . This yields: $P_2^* = \frac{a}{3}$

As the solution is symmetric: $P_1^* = P_2^* = \frac{a}{3}$

This is an NE – neither player has an incentive to deviate from charging this price.

The Car park user pays: $P_1^* + P_2^* = \frac{2a}{3}$

From this, the usage of the car park can be calculated: $Q = \frac{a}{3b}$

Total profit is given by:

$$(P_1^* + P_2^*)Q = \frac{2a^2}{9b}$$

This result can be expanded to N players:

$$P_T^* = \frac{aN}{N+1}$$
$$Q^* = \frac{a}{b(N+1)}$$
$$\text{Total profit:} = \frac{a^2N}{b(N+1)^2}$$

The key point of this exercise is that as N tends to infinity, the number of users of the car park and profit tend to zero. The price of parking tends to 'a'. Eventually the parking lot will be unused, and its value lost – an inefficient outcome. This describes 'the tragedy of the anticommons'.

4.2 Stackelberg Anticommons Game

Secondly, the Stackelberg model introduced by Yoon and Shughart (2013) can be considered. The following equations and analysis are based on their paper – no adaptations have been made at this stage. Yoon and Shughart's paper gives two different types of Stackelberg orderings. The first is each player deciding sequentially (player 1 in round one, player two observing this price and deciding their price in round two, player three observing both rounds before, and deciding their price in round three etc.). The second type is when the first player decides their price in the first round, then all other players decide their price in the second round. Due to its

complexity and the fact that both models reach the same result, only the first of these types will be considered.

This section will go through the same method as seen earlier, but with the Stackelberg Anticommons Game. First, the two-player game is considered. Backwards induction will be used to solve this and show that the result of zero usage occurs even faster when prices are set sequentially.

Given P_1 , player 2 maximises P_2 in the following way: $\max p_2 Q = \frac{p_2(a-p_1-p_2)}{b}$

Taking first order conditions and setting to zero yields player 2's optimal price conditional on player 1's price: $p_2 = \frac{a-p_1}{2}$

Player 1 predicts how player 2 will react to their price set. Therefore, they maximise the following:

$$\max p_1 Q = \frac{p_1(a-p_1-p_2)}{b} = \frac{p_1\left(a-p_1-\left(\frac{a-p_1}{2}\right)\right)}{b}$$

This simplifies to: $\frac{p_1\left(\frac{a-p_1}{2}\right)}{b}$

Setting equal to zero and solving for p_1 gives: $p_1^* = \frac{a}{2}$

Substituting the result into the expression for p_2 gives: $p_2^* = \frac{a}{4}$

$$P_T^* = \frac{3a}{4}$$

$$Q^* = \frac{a}{4b}$$

$$\text{Total profit} = \frac{3a^2}{16b}$$

This is an NE. With only two players it can be shown that the total price is greater in the Stackelberg game, and that the total usage of the car park is lower. There is an

even greater level of inefficiency in the outcome with the Stackelberg model – the tragedy of the anticommons is greater. Expanding to the N player version of this model shows that profit and usage is lower for all N than the simple model. Profit and usage tends to 0 at a much faster rate and price increases at a faster rate. With N players, and fully sequential play, it can be shown that:

$$P_T^* = a\left(1 - \frac{1}{2^N}\right)$$

$$Q^* = a - P_T = \frac{a}{2^N}$$

$$Total\ profit = P_T^*Q^* = \frac{\left[a^2\left(1 - \frac{1}{2^N}\right)\right]}{2^N}$$

4.3 The Optimal Result

Whilst these models are useful to provide a basis in anticommons modelling, it is surprising that both Buchanan and Yoon (2000) and Yoon and Shughart (2013) failed to compare their results to a more optimal outcome. To bridge this shortfall, coordination will be introduced to find an optimal result. This will quantify the loss of profit to the players as well as the loss to society. Whilst several different aspects could be optimised, this paper will maximise revenue to players. By maximising revenue, the analysis can directly show the loss to the players by lack of coordination and selfish use of their excludability rights. This result is identical to the result that will be seen in the bankruptcy adaptation.

Suppose two companies coordinate with each other to maximise revenue. In doing so, they set one price and split the proceeds based on an agreement. Under these conditions, the result is the same as would be found with a monopoly. One might think that this would reduce either quantity, reduce price or decrease societies welfare but as this paper will show, even this monopoly result is less harmful than the result seen with anticommons.

First, rearrange for Q:

$$P_T = P_1 + P_2 = a - bQ$$

$$Q = \frac{a - P_T}{b}$$

Revenue, $R = P_T Q$:

$$R = P_T Q = \frac{P_T(a - P_T)}{b}$$

This time, there is a single variable maximisation problem. Take first order conditions with respect to P_T (maximising revenue with respect to price) and set equal to zero.

$$\frac{dR}{dP_T} = \frac{a - 2P_T}{b} = 0$$

Solving for P_T^* yields:

$$P_T^* = \frac{a}{2}$$

Any result where the following is true is optimal for revenue:

$$P_T^* = P_1^* + P_2^* = \frac{a}{2}$$

Subbing this into quantity and revenue results with:

$$Q^* = \frac{a}{2b}$$

$$\text{Total profit} = P_T^* Q^* = \frac{a^2}{4b}$$

If price and profit are split equally then each person will charge $\frac{a}{4}$ and earn $\frac{a^2}{8b}$.

Generalising this result to N players is easy as each additional player simply coordinates, and the same price is charged (but with an extra player splitting the profit) so the same revenue and quantity is earned.

4.4 Social Welfare

As discussed earlier in the paper, underuse is not always harmful (Bell and Parchomovsky, 2003). To conclude that the underuse found in these two models is harmful, the concept of total surplus (TS) must be introduced. This conclusion is a contribution of this paper and also applies to the loss of value in bankruptcy which will be seen later. TS is commonly interpreted throughout microeconomics as social welfare (Varian, 2014). Producer surplus in this case is just revenue/profit, and consumer surplus is the area of the triangle above equilibrium price.

$$\text{Social Welfare} = \text{Total Surplus} = \text{Consumer Surplus} + \text{Producer Surplus}$$

$$TS = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)((a - P_T^*) * Q^*) + (P_T^* * Q^*)$$

4.5 Comparison of the Results

All the different models can now be brought together for comparison in their simplest two player forms.

Table 1 - Comparison of Models

	Optimal	Simple	Stackelberg
Total Price	$\frac{a}{2}$	$\frac{2a}{3}$	$\frac{3a}{4}$
Revenue/ Profit	$\frac{a^2}{4b}$	$\frac{2a^2}{9b}$	$\frac{3a^2}{16b}$
Quantity	$\frac{a}{2b}$	$\frac{a}{3b}$	$\frac{a}{4b}$
Social Welfare	$\frac{3a^2}{8b}$	$\frac{5a^2}{16b}$	$\frac{7a^2}{32b}$

Total price increases across the models – the optimal model has the lowest price, the simple anticommons model is in the middle and the Stackelberg model has the highest total price. Revenue and quantity have the opposite relationship – the optimal model has the highest revenue and quantity whilst the Stackelberg has the lowest.

Social welfare allows the conclusion that there is a tragedy of the anticommons when excludability rights are introduced. This tragedy of the anticommons deteriorates in a Stackelberg anticommons (less quantity used, and a smaller social welfare compared to both the optimal and simple model result). That said, the simple model is still not efficient – there is still less quantity used compared to the optimal ($\frac{a}{2b}$ vs $\frac{a}{3b}$).

The N-player models can now be plotted graphically. The following analysis is new and has not been taken from Buchanan and Yoon (2000) or Yoon and Shughart (2013). By taking the N-player results, these models can now be plotted graphically to see how

total revenue, quantity and total price react to changes in the number of excluders. For simplicity $a = 1$, $b = 1$.

Figure 3 - Simple Model Plot

As the number of excluders increases, both revenue and quantity decrease. This effect starts to flatten out – the decrease in quantity and price is diminishing.

Figure 4 - Stackelberg Model Plot

As the number of excluders increases, both revenue and quantity decrease. This effect starts to flatten out much faster than in the simple model – use is almost zero at N equals seven.

Figure 5 - Optimal Model Plot

There is no excluding and therefore no loss from exclusion or the threat of exclusion. There is no inefficiency – revenue, quantity and price stay constant.

Figure 6 - Total Revenue - Simple Model vs Stackelberg Model vs Optimal Model

Total revenue falls significantly faster when using the Stackelberg model. This means that value is destroyed faster when each excluder only excludes those behind them in an ordering. Tragedy of the anticommons is more severe.

5. Simple and Stackelberg Anticommons Games in Bankruptcy

The following chapter will show that with a few simple adaptations, the two anticommons models can be used to understand the main dynamics in bankruptcy and predict inefficiencies. This adaptation is a key contribution of this paper. The purpose for this adaptation is to end up with a model that fits the bankruptcy purpose whilst retaining the key aspects of the models that allowed for the analysis in terms of quantity and social welfare.

The interpretation of the model's parameters can now be changed for this application:

1. Q is the post-bankruptcy value of the company.
2. P is assets taken out of the company by debtholders/ cost of constraints and demands put on the company⁵.
3. a is the maximum recoverable value of the company.
4. b is the sensitivity of the company's post-bankruptcy value to restructuring demands/ assets taken out of the company by the debtors.

Q_L is the estimated liquidation value of the company. This can be calculated by traditional valuation methods. In any bankruptcy where this exceeds the estimated value of the reorganised company post-bankruptcy, the company will be liquidated. Additionally, if an agreement is unable to be reached, assume that the company will be liquidated or sold at the Q_L price.

Suppose a company has gone bankrupt with one fulcrum class⁶ of debt. In this class, there are two debt holders: Person 1 and Person 2. Person 1 holds 60% of the debt class and Person 2 holds 40% of the debt class. Any agreement to restructuring would require 75% of the debt to vote in favour of the agreement. In this case, both people must agree for a deal to be accepted and therefore, both have excludability rights. This implies that an anticommons model is appropriate. Since both debt holders are

⁵ To exclude, debt holders can set unreasonably high constraints for the reorganised company.

⁶ An impaired class of debt – the owners of which have a say in proceedings.

in the same class and have the same rights, the simple anticommons model is the most appropriate.

Suppose that the company holds a contract to supply a manufacturer – this is cancelled automatically upon declaring bankruptcy. This means the maximum restructuring value of the company is 90%. Suppose the company is slightly inelastic to the demands and restrictions it will face post-bankruptcy. Its elasticity to demands is 0.8.

This gives:

$$a = 0.9$$

$$b = 0.8$$

The two people now maximise revenue using their beliefs about the other person. Using the analysis methods from the simple model (Buchanan and Yoon, 2000):

$$P_1^* = P_2^* = \frac{a}{3} = 0.3$$

$$P^* = P_1^* + P_2^* = 0.6$$

Post-Bankruptcy company value is given by:

$$Q = \frac{a}{3b} = 0.375 = 37.5\%$$

'Profit' (interpreted here as reorganisation efficiency) is given by: $(P_1^* + P_2^*)Q = \frac{2a^2}{9b}$

$$\frac{2a^2}{9b} = 0.225 = 22.5\%$$

By itself, this numerical example only shows a simple application of the adapted bankruptcy model. Shortly, the same analysis will be done using the optimal model to allow for comparison.

For a more complex (Stackelberg) example, suppose again that the same company has gone bankrupt – with the same elasticity to creditor demands and the same maximum reorganisation value. This time there are three fulcrum classes of debt and three investors. Person 1 owns 100% of Class A debt; Person 2 owns 100% of Class B debt; and Person 3 owns 100% of Class C debt. Additionally, Person 2 has won a legal battle with the company that allows it to be the sole proposer of reorganisations. The dollar amounts of Class A, Class B and Class C debt are set so that both Person 1 and Person 2, with Class A and Class B debt respectively, have less than 25% of the outstanding fulcrum class debt. Class C debt makes up the majority of fulcrum class debt. Normally, in line with the cramdown provision, this would imply that Person 1 or 2 can be excluded from any deal so long as Person 3, with Class C debt, agrees to a deal. However, Person 2 is the sole proposer of reorganisations. This means they will only suggest something acceptable to them – they have a slightly weaker means to exclude. Person 3 also has excludability rights – with a significant amount of the outstanding debt they can solely reject any reorganisation they do not like. This means that Person 3 holds the most power, then person 2 and finally Person 1 who can be excluded completely from any reorganisation. Since Person 1 is excluded, they cannot make any demands so the two player Stackelberg Anticommons Model can be used:

Person 1 and Person 2 maximise their demands, but Person 2 does so subject to their beliefs about Person 1's demands.

$$p_1^* = \frac{a}{2} = 0.45$$

$$p_2^* = \frac{a}{4} = 0.225$$

Total demands are the summed demands:

$$P^* = \frac{3a}{4} = 0.675$$

The reorganisation value of the company is therefore:

$$Q^* = \frac{a}{4b} = \frac{9}{32} = 28.13\%$$

This result shows that the reorganised value of the company is significantly less than the simple anticommons outcome model. This implies that Stackelberg excludability rights are destructive to reorganised firm value.

'Profit' (reorganisation efficiency) is given by: $(P_1^* + P_2^*)Q^* = \frac{3a^2}{16b}$

$$\frac{3a^2}{16b} = 0.1898 = 18.98\%$$

This can be compared to both the optimal figure and the outcome reached in the simple model.

$$P_T = P_1 + P_2 = \frac{a}{2} = 0.45$$

$$Q^* = \frac{a}{2b} = 0.5625 = 56.25\%$$

'Profit' (reorganisation efficiency) is given by: $(P_1^* + P_2^*)Q^* = \frac{a^2}{4b}$

$$\frac{a^2}{4b} = 25.31\%$$

In this adaptation, 'underuse' is derived from the fact that the reorganised company's value (Q) is lower than it would be in the optimal example – its value is underused. From this comparison, it can be suggested that underuse is the outcome in both the simple and the Stackelberg examples - when compared to the optimal outcome. Additionally, when one person can exclude those beneath them, and the second person under those beneath them (example 2), the underuse is more extreme and the tragedy of the anticommons more severe. Excludability rights stemming from credit in bankruptcy situations causes destruction of value in this model.

These conclusions match what can be seen in figure 6. Whilst the model makes no suggestions to long term returns, the model does suggest that anticommons encourages short term grappling of value by encouraging stronger demands (P) and is likely to reduce the long-term value of the restructured company.

Despite the favourable conclusions, the simple and the Stackelberg anticommons models are not without flaws.

One flaw is the major simplification of the bankruptcy procedure. Bankruptcy is dynamic, procedural and influenceable by outside parties. In the Baird and Rasmussen payoff model, this paper already discussed how renegotiating and the dynamics of bankruptcy lead to oversimplified models - the same is true here. These models are capable of providing a theoretical understanding once a bankruptcy has concluded. They are unable to account for multiple steps of negotiation or provide any step-by-step insights. Their value is theoretical and backwards looking.

Additionally, the bankruptcy process does sometimes have protection from anticommons – a judge. This is changeable from case to case and therefore cannot be modelled, but judges have the ability to force through deals, even if parties are unwilling. In extreme cases they can set deadlines where a breach forces liquidation of a company. In Merced's article (2009), the example of bankrupt company, Delphi, is discussed. Negotiations for reorganisation were long and unsuccessful. Eventually the judge allowed a government organised sale to a private equity institution. The

valuation was extremely low, and this threat pushed creditors to finalise an agreement to take over the company – alleviating the tragedy of the anticommons. However, whilst the threat of a lower return can help relieve anticommons, judges are largely unwilling to overreach – a theme discussed in Talley and Pandya (2023).

For these models to provide valuable insights, they must be considered as solely backwards looking and theoretical. They have value in explaining economic inefficiencies that can arise in bankruptcies and provide a route to quantifying this inefficiency. These models hold no predictive power and do not offer policy suggestions. They are abstract to many dynamics, costs and constraints that are present in real world bankruptcy.

That said, this conclusion is similar to the conclusion reached when analysing the initial car park model which the bankruptcy adaptation was based on (Buchanan and Yoon, 2000). In the car park model, the term b can be interpreted as price's sensitivity to a change in the car park's fullness. In reality, the vast majority of parkers do not care if the car park is 0% or 95% full – this is not what the model would suggest (unless $b = 0$, in which case $P_T = a$, and the analysis is irrelevant anyway). The point this is making is: the fact that the bankruptcy model is flawed does not matter for its purpose. In the same way the car park model is a useful way to think about anticommons and property rights, the bankruptcy model is a useful way to think about anticommons and bankruptcy.

6. Conclusion

The goal of this paper was to build a case for the application of anticommons, and its related models, to bankruptcy. This was successful and resulted in theoretical conclusions from the bankruptcy adapted anticommons models (Buchanan and Yoon, 2000; Yoon and Shughart, 2013). This was achieved in the following way: firstly, literature was used to show that both excludability rights and fragmented creditor interests can be found in the bankruptcy setting. This showed that anticommons is possible in bankruptcy and allowed for the analysis of three different game-theoretic models: the Baird Rasmussen model, the Simple anticommons model and the Stackelberg anticommons model. From these models, and this paper's own furthering of Buchanan and Yoon (2000) and Yoon and Shughart's (2013), the following can be said: tragedy of the anticommons is a plausible and likely outcome in bankruptcy.

The model derived from Baird and Rasmussen (2010) explains how incentives amongst creditors may not be aligned. This shows that stakeholders may be incentivised to not form a partnership – even when a partnership preserves the most value in the reorganised company. Despite the finding, this model is flawed by its lack of ability to incorporate renegotiating, excludability, and other dynamics. This meant further analysis was still needed.

Next, the paper built upon Buchanan and Yoon's (2000) and Yoon and Shughart's (2013) simple and Stackelberg anticommons models. By developing an optimal result, the fullness of car parks (shown by Q) in the anticommons models could be compared to show that neither model achieves an efficient result with two players. This was generalised graphically – car park availability decreased as the number of excluders increases. The subsequent adaptation to bankruptcy allows for this result to carry over – implying that value is lost to the reorganised company when it is possible for debt holders to exclude. The higher the number of excluders, the higher the value loss. It was also shown that this effect is more severe in a sequential game (Stackelberg model).

Through this paper's use of total surplus and welfare to society, it can be concluded that society loses as a result of underuse in a bankruptcy. This is a tragedy of the anticommons. When each debt holder treats bankruptcy like a game, and acts optimally, this will be the result. If the debt holders were to work together, they would maximise the reorganised value of the company. Instead, debt holders maximise their own reorganised value by putting stringent demands on the company.

However, the real-world usage of this adaptation is limited by a number of assumptions and simplifications present in the model. By ignoring negotiation, costs, and dynamics like judge intervention in the analysis, the models only provide a simple a teachable framework to explain anticommons in bankruptcy. That said, this is exactly the same as the well-acclaimed car park model presented by nobel laureate Buchanan and the co-author Yoon (2000). This model is never and will never be used in real time to optimise car parks. It is a useful tool to explain and learn the theory behind anticommons whilst demonstrating its applications. In doing so, the word 'anticommons' is being spread and further understood – a key step required in solving the anticommons tragedy according to Heller (2013).

This brings the paper on to recommending future research. The most crucial aspects of future research can be split into three categories: real anticommons in US bankruptcy, geographical possibility of anticommons in bankruptcy, and stand-alone modelling of anticommons in bankruptcy. Finding real world examples of anticommons in bankruptcy would help to determine if US bankruptcy is more susceptible to anticommons. By investigating other developed countries for a lack of anticommons, future research may determine how these countries have either avoided fragmented creditor interests or not given creditors excludability rights. This may allow of policy suggestions to avert this in the US. Finally, a purpose designed model for anticommons in bankruptcy would allow for better modelling of the loss of value and efficiency. This would mean better estimates of the scale of the problem and may help to inform a policy approach.

To conclude (using Fennell's (2005) lock and key analogy from the introduction):

In the right circumstances, the full value of a reorganised company can be seen as a garden. Debt holders each hold a key and are able to stop one another from realising the full potential value of the garden (the company). When there are misaligned incentives and excludability rights, collective value can be destroyed – a tragedy of the anticommons. This is a tragedy that US bankruptcy law must reckon with.

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